

Maintainers and restorers for WA cytoplasmic source (V20 A)

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Screening locally adapted elite breeding lines for genetically diverse maintainers and restorers for different cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines is important in developing new CMS lines.

We used 37 National Screening Nursery entries as pollen parents for crossing with stable WA-type CMS line V20 A. The F₁ hybrids were grown in a well-puddled field. During anthesis, anthers from 10-15 spikelets each of 3 panicles of individual F₁ plants were collected at random. They were examined under a microscope, using Lugol's iodine solution, and pollen sterility estimated. Spikelet fertility was estimated on two to three panicles that had been bagged on each hybrid plant.

Varieties were classified as effective maintainers (spikelet fertility less than 1%), weak maintainers (spikelet fertility less than 25%), partial restorers (spikelet fertility 25-79%), and effective restorers (spikelet fertility more than 80%). IET10158, IET10428, IET10849, IET10851, IET11721, IET11811, IET11668, and IET10503 were effective maintainers; IET10830, IET9819, IET10458, IET9979, IET9798, IET11057, IET10462, IET10463, IET10435, and IET11722 were effective restorers for V20 A (see table). The effective maintainers will be used to develop new CMS lines possessing WA cytoplasm with different nuclear backgrounds, using recurrent backcrossing procedures.

Fertility restoration of National Screening Nursery varieties in test crosses with V20 A of wild abortive source. CRRRI, 1990.

Genotype	Parentage	V20 A (F ₁)		M/R ^a
		Pollen fertility (%)	Spikelet fertility (%)	
IET10158	Swarnadhan/NLR9674	0	0	M
IET10428	IR4219-35-3/IR4.570	0	0	M
IET11350	Bas370/CRR88-1-7-1-3	10.0	9.6	WM
IET10849	CR157-392/OR 67-21	0	0	M
IET11062 ^b	B29826/SR62-31-4	54.6	49.9	PRIM
IET12020	Sona/Basmati 370	9.1	7.0	WM
IET10851	Samridhi/IR36	0	0	M
IET11721		0	0	M
IET11811	IR36/TR17	0	0	M
IET11668	Co. 37/6551	0.6	0	M
IET10881 ^c	Ryllored/Palman	64.8	61.5	PRIM
IET10983 ^d	WGL23022/Surekha	73.8	71.7	PRIM
IET10503	Sona/IR28	0	0	M
IET10451	T90/IR8//RPW 6-13/// Siam 29/Mahsuri	8.2	6.0	WM
IET9994	Sona/ARC14529	15.0	13.1	WM
IET10763	IR36/IET7916	24.8	21.1	WM
IET9831	Prasanna/IR50	23.0	15.3	WM
IET9292	CO13/IR26	16.0	12.6	WM
IET11004	ES280/1-2/Ptb 33	49.7	29.6	PR
IET11785		69.1	61.8	PR
IET10516	Phalguna/TKM6	45.3	40.8	PR
IET9824	Rasi/Dular	70.1	63.8	PR
IET11001	IR36///Suphala/PR3880// CR222/Parijat	32.9	28.6	PR
IET10508	IR50/IET7918	50.0	44.7	PR
IET9288	Jaya/Ptb 33	60.6	44.5	PR
IET9961	IR8 mutant	70.0	63.9	PR
IET9586	IET4141/CR98-7216	58.6	29.9	PR
IET10830	CR157-392/OR57-21	94.7	80.0	R
IET9819	Ratna/Zagar	96.8	91.5	R
IET10458	IET2886/Annapuma	92.1	81.0	R
IET9979	Phalguna/IR50	87.3	84.5	R
IET9798	Pusa 186-10-45/Pusa 2-21	84.9	83.2	R
IET11057	Rasi/IET7332	86.4	81.5	R
IET10462	Nam Sagui 19/IR4215// IR9219-209-3-2	91.6	89.5	R
IET10463		92.1	91.1	R
IET10435	Sel. from IRTP 12140	89.7	87.4	R
IET11722	IET7615/RP79-5	94.1	83.5	R

^aM = maintainer, R = restorer, P = partial, W = weak. ^bIET11062: 40% of F₁ plants completely sterile. ^cIET10881: 66.7% of F₁ plants highly sterile (96.8-99.1% pollen sterility). ^dIET10983: 20% of F₁ plants completely sterile.

IET11062, IET10881, and IET10983 were both effective maintainers and partial restorers for V20 A. This indicates that these three varieties might have

heterozygous fertility restoration genes; they interacted differently with CMS line V20 A. □

New CMS line Zaoxian A with incomplete dominance of short duration

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The growth duration of hybrid combinations used in commercial rice production in China (Shanyou 63, Weiyou 64) is mainly determined by restorer lines. To shorten the growth duration of hybrid rices for a cropping system of rice - wheat - rice or rice - rape - rice and to extend hybrid combinations derived from long-duration restorer lines to short-

duration rice regions and to mountainous, high altitude regions, we developed a CMS line with incomplete dominance of short duration.

In 1985, we crossed Zhenshan 97 B with a shorter duration plant selected from the F₂ of *O. longistaminata* / Liuzhou wild rice (*O. sativa* L. f. *spontanea*). Zhenshan 97 A was backcrossed with